

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D2.1 Prioritisation criteria report WP 2

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
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Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 2

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RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Version	Date	Reviewer name/institution	Short description of changes
1	12 th January 2023	T2.1 partners and MB members	General comments
2	13 th February 2023		Minor changes following the comments on version 1

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 3

Abstract

The identification of the first set of priorities for PARC started before the launch of the Partnership with the legacy from HBM4EU and with a survey sent to the interim governing board members. In order to have a clearer view on the prioritisation strategy within the different WPs, a survey dedicated to the prioritisation of substances and meetings with WPLs and TLs to discuss the prioritisation of methods took place after the beginning of PARC. Many criteria were identified on the basis of which the prioritisation was made. For the upcoming years, in order to best achieve the objectives of PARC, a process to prioritise the activities will be implemented and consists of i) Mapping of the regulatory needs, ii) Scoring/ranking of activities based on specific priority criteria and, iii) Preparing Background/ Scoping documents. It has to be noted that managing the priorities of a large-scale partnership is challenging but with the right planning targets can be reached.

Key Words

Prioritisation criteria, Regulatory needs, Chemical risk assessment, HBM4EU legacy, PARC priorities, Substances, Methods

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 4

Table of contents

Technical References	2
Document history	2
Abstract	3
Key Words	3
Table of contents	4
List of Tables	5
List of Figures	6
Annexes	6
Abbreviations	7
1. Authors and Acknowledgments	8
2. Introduction	9
2.1 Context	9
2.2 Objectives	10
2.3 How the deliverable was prepared	10
3. Identification of Priorities for PARC	10
3.1 Background: HBM4EU legacy	10
3.2 PARC Interim GB survey	12
4. Feedback from the WPs on their prioritisation strategy for the first years	21
4.1 Prioritisation of substances: launch of a dedicated survey	22
4.2 Prioritisation of methods: organisation of bilateral meetings	22
5. Outcomes of the prioritisation process	23
5.1 Substances	23
5.2 Methods	25
6. Discussion	28
7. Conclusion and Perspective	31
Annexes	34

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

Co-funded by
the European Union

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 5

List of Tables

Table 1: Reduced list of the prioritised substances following the HBM4EU stakeholder workshop.....	12
Table 2: PARC Interim GB nominations on the short list of substances within WP4 for HBM, Environmental and multisource monitoring for human exposure and, for Environmental monitoring in the context of environmental risk assessment	13
Table 3: Ranking of substance priorities (1=high to 4=low) within WP5 for human health studies	15
Table 4: Ranking of substance priorities (1=high to 4 =low) within WP5 for environmental health studies	15
Table 5: Ranking of endpoint priorities (1=high to 5 =low) within WP5 according to human health studies	15
Table 6: Interim GB suggestions of endpoints to be considered under WP5.....	16
Table 7: Ranking of the methodology priorities under WP5 (1=high to 5=low) for human health	17
Table 8: Ranking of the methodology priorities under WP5 (1=high to 5=low) for environmental studies.....	17
Table 9: Ranking of toxicological endpoints of higher priority for which IATAs should be developed under Task 6.1	18
Table 10: Ranking of case studies of higher priority for IERA under Task 6.2	18
Table 11: Suggestions of case studies for integrative exposure and ecological risk assessment under Task 6.2	19
Table 12: Suggestions of case studies for the Review of risk assessment methodologies under Task 6.3.....	20
Table 13: PARC interim GB suggestions for case studies under Task 6.4	21
Table 14: Ranking of the four criteria for the prioritisation of substances for the human health studies depending on their importance.....	23
Table 15: Ranking of the four criteria for the prioritisation of group of substances for environmental health studies depending on their importance.....	24
Table 16: Substances / Group of substances covered under each WP	29
Table 17: Short list of 25 substances from the 3 rd prioritisation round of HBM4EU	35
Table 18: The interim GB's suggestions for activities to be developed under Task 4.3 for the first three years of PARC	36

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

Co-funded by
the European Union

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 6

Table 19: List of the Projects covering Substances/ Group of substances under the different WPs..... 41

List of Figures

Figure 1: Parallel prioritisation processes that fed into PARC 11
Figure 2: Prioritisation process for the upcoming years of PARC 33
Figure 3: Process for project reviewing and the life cycle of the project 34

Annexes

Annex 1: Project Life Cycle..... 34
Annex 2: Short list of 25 substances within the 3rd prioritisation round of HBM4EU..... 35
Annex 3: Interim GB’s suggestions for activities to be developed under task 4.3 36
Annex 4: Survey on the criteria for the prioritisation of substances within the first years of PARC 39
Annex 5: List of the projects covering Substances/ Group of substances under the different WPs..... 41

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 7

Abbreviations

ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
ASR	Annual Summary Report
AWP	Annual Work Plan
CLs	Chemical Leaders
CSS	Chemical strategy for sustainability
CT	Coordination Team
ED	Endocrine Disruptors/ Disruption
EDA	Effect-Directed Analysis
EDC	Endocrine Disrupting Compounds
GB	PARC Governing Board
GSB	PARC Grant Signatory Board
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	Human Biomonitoring for EU
IERA	Integrative exposure and risk assessment
MB	PARC Management Board
MDC	Metabolic Disrupting Compounds
MLs	Methodology Leaders
NHs	PARC National Hubs
PARC	Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
PBT	Persistent, Bio-accumulative and Toxic
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances
QSAR	Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship
RA	Risk Assessment
RRM	Rapid Response Mechanism
SNTS	Suspect Non-Targeted Screening
SRIA	PARC rolling Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SRIP	Strategic Research and Innovation Plan for safe and sustainable chemicals and materials
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable-by-Design
TK	Toxicokinetics
TL	PARC Task co-Leader
TransGen	Transgenerational effects, epigenetics and delayed effects
vPvB	very Persistent and very Bio-accumulative
WP	PARC Work Package
WPL	PARC Work Package co-Leader

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 8

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EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 9

2. Introduction

2.1 Context

WP2, “A common science-policy-agenda”, has the specific role of prioritising activities within PARC and providing input regarding their regulatory processes. This can be achieved by ensuring the alignment of the research work done with the regulatory needs at national, EU or international levels and, by making sure the results are planned in a timely matter to support regulatory uptake.

Within WP2, Task 2.1 “Priority Setting” is responsible for coordinating the prioritisation process and providing input regarding regulatory processes and timelines to the PARC Management Board (MB). Projects and activities implemented under PARC should provide added value to the regulatory needs for risk assessment and risk management. This should be true on the national or EU level, considering the goals of the EU Chemical’s strategy on sustainability¹ and the Green Deal’s zero-pollution ambition for a toxic free environment. For that, Task 2.1 Co-leaders and partners are developing a proposal for an overall PARC prioritisation process, drawing on the legacy of HBM4EU and further achievements within the preparation phase of PARC. A process for reviewing project proposals under PARC was approved (**Annex 1**).

A project within PARC is considered as any activity, inter-connected activity and case study that will generate data and/or knowledge to answer PARC objectives. It has to be attached to one principal WP and task (with possible links to other tasks/projects); it should have a “start” date and an “end” date, a responsible called “Project Manager” and a dedicated team with associated budget (PMs and other costs). The number of partners should not exceed preferably 25 and should include preferably at least 3 different countries. The project initiation begins with WP Leaders (WPLs) / Task Leaders (TLs), which are responsible for identifying projects (with the WP/Task participants) to answer to priorities according to the WP/Task objectives.

For the first year of PARC, projects have been included in the work plan before the development of the review process. Nevertheless, all of them had been discussed and undergone refinement to ensure their alignment with PARC objectives and their scientific quality. In this context, TLs and WPLs had to explain how each project contributes to the

¹ EU Chemical’s strategy on sustainability: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0667>

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 10

regulatory remit of PARC. From year two, new projects had to follow the project review process.

2.2 Objectives

This deliverable describes how the priorities for PARC have been identified and addressed in the planned activities of the partnership. As PARC is not only dealing with filling the gaps in the terms of exposure or toxicity of specific compounds / groups of compounds, but also is dealing with new methods to investigate either the exposure in various matrices or the pathways of toxicity, the priorities have to be adapted to both fields.

Some criteria more adapted for the substances/groups of substances were identified, whereas, for the methods, other parameters have been considered. The criteria are related to the hazardous properties of the substance/group and/or the exposure and /or the risks, either for human health or for the environment. For the methods, this deliverable discusses criteria to identify the areas for which new methods and other innovative tools should be developed or standardised or pre-validated.

2.3 How the deliverable was prepared

The deliverable report of HBM4EU² “D4.10: 2nd Report on stakeholder consultation and mapping of needs” and, the compilation of the feedback from the survey sent to the interim GB of PARC helped identify the priorities of this partnership long before its launch; these elements are developed in Section 3 of this document. Moreover, a survey for the criteria for the prioritisation of substances and several meetings that took place with the WPLs and TLs during year 1 of PARC allowed the mapping of the prioritisation strategy within the WPs, these are developed in Section 4 of this deliverable.

3. Identification of Priorities for PARC

3.1 Background: HBM4EU³ legacy

During the preparation of PARC it was agreed that this partnership will build on work undertaken as part of HBM4EU and will broaden the scope of its interests, specifically on the assessment of environmental risks.

² Deliverable D4.10 of HBM4EU: [Deliverable-4.10-2nd-Report-on-stakeholder-consultation-and-mapping-of-needs.pdf \(hbm4eu.eu\)](#)

³ HBM4EU description site: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/733032>

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 11

The HBM4EU project was launched in 2016 with the aim of improving the collective understanding of human exposure to hazardous chemicals and developing HBM as an exposure assessment method. The project ended in June 2022.

Consequently, two prioritisation processes in HBM4EU fed into PARC, they are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Parallel prioritisation processes that fed into PARC

The results of the two prioritisation processes fed the development of the PARC proposal. Then, it was the responsibility of the PARC interim consortium to:

- Discuss, rank and agree on priorities for each work package and across work packages;
- Translate priorities into research activities and infrastructure needs; and
- Develop activities for inclusion in the PARC rolling Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) for the proposal.

In fact, three prioritisation rounds took place in the course of HBM4EU.

The first list of HBM4EU priority substances was identified in 2016. The second round of prioritisation was then conducted from 2017 to 2018. A third round of prioritisation was done from 2020 to 2021 to identify priorities for research under PARC. Within this latest round, an online survey was conducted allowing HBM4EU National Hubs, members of the EU Policy Board and the Stakeholder Forum to nominate substances for Human Biomonitoring (HBM) research. Participants were asked to nominate up to five substances or groups of substances and provide their chemical name and CAS number. They could also nominate chemical mixtures and emerging substances – as groups of substances.

As a result, a long list of all substances nominated by the survey participants was produced. This long list was then reduced to a short list of 25 substances taking into consideration

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 12

substances nominated by the members of the EU Policy Board and those nominated by more than one survey participant (**Annex 2**). Afterwards, draft background documents were generated for each substance/substance group of the shortlist (prioritisation criteria, namely hazard properties, exposure characteristics, regulatory status, public concern and technical feasibility). The aim was to identify knowledge gaps that might be addressed through activities of the project.

Following this, a stakeholder workshop was organised, to gather input from the members of the stakeholder forum and a broader range of stakeholders on their concerns regarding substances on the short list. During the workshop, an online voting was organised to identify substances to be the focus of discussion. Each nominating entity was allowed to nominate three substances. Some substances received the same number of nominations and were therefore ranked together. The results of the nominations are available in the Table below (**Table 1**).

Table 1: Reduced list of the prioritised substances following the HBM4EU stakeholder workshop

Rank	Substance	Number of votes
1	PFAS	19
2	Trace/Heavy Metals	10
3	Pesticides and Biocides (with Fungicides)	9
4	Flame Retardants Mixtures	7
5	Fungicides Industrial solvents Emerging substances	5
6	Mercury	4
7	Metals in batteries Aluminium and Manganese Persistent Organic Pollutants Synthetic Fragrances Bisphenols Mycotoxins Endocrine Disruptors	3

3.2 PARC Interim GB survey

The overview of priorities identified by the interim PARC Work Package (WP) co-leaders was based on the results of the survey on prioritisation conducted over the summer 2020 and further discussions between the interim Management Board (MB) and WP task forces implemented in the autumn 2020. It was sent to the PARC interim Grant Signatory Board (GSB) and interim Governing Board (GB) members ahead of the first joint interim GSB and GB

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 13

meeting on 01/12/2020, during which it was presented. The overview and presentation at the meeting also highlighted some main issues for which input from the interim GB was needed in each WP. For this reason, a form was sent on 15/01/2021 to the interim GB to be filled-in by 19/02/2021. The GB representative had to consult and coordinate with GSB of its country to provide a response. Only one response was allowed per country. Questions in the survey were addressed per WP or Task.

- **Identification of needs concerning “Monitoring and exposure” (WP4)**

WP4 consists of 3 tasks. **Task 4.1** concerns Human Biomonitoring (HBM) whereas **Task 4.2** is mainly about Environmental and multisource monitoring.

Through the survey sent to the PARC interim GB, votes were gathered on the main priorities of **substances/group of substances** for the first three years of PARC: 1-HBM, 2- Environmental and multisource monitoring for human exposure, 3- Environmental monitoring in the context of environmental risk assessment. The total number of nominations (national + EU) for the requested substances/group of substances from the short list from HBM4EU is represented in the table below (Table 2).

Table 2: PARC Interim GB nominations on the short list of substances within WP4 for HBM, Environmental and multisource monitoring for human exposure and, for Environmental monitoring in the context of environmental risk assessment

Substance name	Total No of nominations		
	HBM ⁴	Env M for H ⁵	Env M for ENV ⁶
Mercury	2	1	1
Trace/heavy metals (e.g.: Al, Co, Mn, Cd, Pb, Cu, Zn, Ni, Cr, W, natural U, Bi, Beryllium, manganese, nickel, arsenic, lithium, vanadium, antimony);	8	5	1
Metals in batteries: cobalt (Co), Nickel, (Ni), Lithium (Li). Nanoforms of Co and Ni	4		1
Acrylamide	1	1	1
PFAS	12	12	10
Flame retardants: Brominated flame retardants, Organophosphate flame retardants, Flame retardants (including TDCPP, TBBPA) (DBDPE, Decabromo-diphenyl ethane, CAS: 84852-53-9, EC: 284-366-9)	6	4	3

⁴ HBM: Human Biomonitoring

⁵ Env M for H: Environmental and multisource monitoring for human exposure

⁶ Env M for ENV: Environmental monitoring in the context of environmental risk assessment

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 14

Pesticides and biocides, with focus on glyphosate, pyrethroids, carbamate, Dithiocarbamates, organophosphates	5	11	8
Fungicides: includes SDHI fungicides (boscalid, bixafen, fluxapyroxad); Azoles (imazalil, ipconazole, metconazole, penconazole, prochloraz, tebuconazole, tetraconazole); Dithiocarbamates; Famoxadone and Dimoxystrobin; Isothiazolinones (CIT/MIT, BIT), Triazole derivative metabolites (TDM)	1	1	2
Phthalates and substitutes, FCM phthalate substitutes, DEHP (Bis(2-ethylhexyl) terephthalate) CAS 6422-86-2	1	2	1
Industrial solvents (e.g. BTEX metabolites, dry cleaning solvents, paint solvents)		1	1
Persistent Organic Pollutants of Increasing Concern such as Dechloranes, Chlorinated paraffins and Chloronaphthalene, Dioxins and PCB	5	9	3
Synthetic fragrances (OTNE-Tetramethyl acetyloctahydronaphthalene, Galaxolide, Lysmeral/Lilial CAS 80-54-6, Polycyclic musks, Lyrall CAS 31906-04-4, Hydroxycitronellal CAS 107-75-5, Isoeugenol CAS 97-54-1)			1
Mixtures (including contaminants e.g. Mycotoxins and plant contaminants, and air pollutants with EDC properties)	2	1	2
Medical substances: occupational		1	8
Bisphenols (BADGE/DGEBA, Bisphenol-A-diglycidylether / Diglycidylether of Bisphenol A, CAS Number: 1675-54-3 EC Number: 216-823-5 and Tetrabromo-bisphenol A (TBBPA); 3-1 Tetrabromobisphenol A)			1
Emerging substances, unknowns, non-targeted screening	1	1	5
Nanomaterials, nanoplastics, nano titanium dioxide			2
Mycotoxins, in particular Ochratoxin A (CAS 303-47-9). Emerging and endocrine active mycotoxins.	1	2	
Endocrine disruptors			5
MOAH Mineral oil aromatic hydrocarbons	1	1	1
Microplastics			6
Cyclic siloxanes			1
Cosmetic Ingredients			2
Persistent and mobile pollutant			2
Volatile Organic Compounds			1
Plasticisers and related products (bisphenols, siloxanes, PCBs, Phthalates, etc)			1

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 15

Within this WP, **Task 4.3** is about innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys. Suggestions for **activities** to be developed under this task for the first three years of PARC are detailed in Table 18 (**Annex 3**).

- **Identification of needs concerning “Hazard assessment” (WP5)**

WP5 consists of 3 tasks. **Task 5.1** is mainly about Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern, **Task 5.2** is about the development of Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling; and **Task 5.3** is a transversal task that addresses the regulatory use of hazard data.

- **Substances** to consider under this WP were ranked in terms of priority from 1 (high) to 4 (low) according to human health and environmental health studies. Results are presented in the tables below (Table 3 and Table 4).

Table 3: Ranking of substance priorities (1=high to 4=low) within WP5 for human health studies

Rank Human Health	1	2	3	4
PFAS	11	5	2	1
Toxins	8	6	2	2
BPA	5	6	3	4
Degradation Products	5	5	5	3

Table 4: Ranking of substance priorities (1=high to 4 =low) within WP5 for environmental health studies

Rank Environmental Health	1	2	3	4
PFAS	7	6	1	
Toxins		4	5	6
BPA	2	6	5	3
Degradation Products	7	6	1	

- **Endpoints**

- Endpoints for **human health** that should be considered within this WP were ranked in terms of priority from 1 (high) to 5 (low). The results can be seen in the table below (Table 5).

Table 5: Ranking of endpoint priorities (1=high to 5 =low) within WP5 according to human health studies

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 16

Rank	1	2	3	4	5
Immunotox	4	6	2	3	2
TransGen	4	7	2	2	1
Mixtures	12	4		1	
ED	8	7	2	1	
Other	6	1	4	1	3

- **Ecotoxicological** endpoints suggested by the countries represented in the PARC interim GB to be considered under WP5 are represented in Table 6.

Table 6: Interim GB suggestions of endpoints to be considered under WP5

Belgium	Ecotoxicological endpoints of interest include impaired development, impaired growth, impaired reproduction, and any endpoint that leads to mortality (including, e.g., impaired swimming performance, impaired visual function, etc.). AOPs can support the necessary linkages to endpoints of regulatory concern (survival, growth and reproduction) which generally all lead to decreased population size as the final adverse outcome. // ED: lack of data for insects, incl. pollinators
Czech Republic	Neurodevelopmental effects (and related neurotoxicity), ED-related effects – namely effects on reproduction (e.g. anti-androgenicity), hier-tier effects (e.g. dung beetle diversity disrupted by antiparasitic veterinary drugs)
Denmark	Development of thyroid-sensitive endpoints in test guidelines for endocrine disrupting effects in fish [SDU] and Developing potential endpoints in fish or amphibians that can be used to predict effects in mammals - including humans – read-across.[SDU] eller Development of tests and sensitive endpoints for endocrine disrupting chemicals in invertebrates and may become part of an ‘Early Warning System’ [SDU]
France	Quantitative AOP base elements to link bisphenol environmental exposure, biomarker dynamic responses and long-term combined effects at the population level in fish. Regulatory interest: To enhance ecological risk assessment, modelling offers a powerful tool to integrate the effects observed in lower tier laboratory studies with the environmental conditions under which exposure is expected in the field. Models can be applied to predict the effects at biologically relevant levels supporting risk management such as the population level starting from environmental exposures and laboratory toxicity data measured at the (sub)organism level. These different models will be the base elements of a future quantitative AOP. Using this modelling framework new insights could be obtained on the interaction mechanisms for the most hazardous substances within a complex mixture, bioaccumulation of these substances can be predicted under different long-term exposure scenarios and the long-term combined effects at the population level could be predicted.
Germany	Neurotoxicity in fish, Test systems for growth inhibition modulators
Italy	Methods for amphibians and other poorly addressed species; embryotoxicity endpoints through the use of FET (zebrafish embryo toxicity test in compliance with 3R principle).
Norway	Behaviour related deviations, microbial resistance, histopathological changes (cancer, liver-changes, etc.), neurotoxicology, teratogenic effects,

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 17

Slovenia	Reproductive toxicity. Acute and chronic toxicity test data for pharmaceuticals in environmental compartments, development of strategy for testing ecotoxic effect for micro and nanoplastic particles and filaments.
Spain	Endocrine disrupter properties for environmental end-points, mobile properties of substances
Switzerland	Ecotoxicological information on pharmaceuticals

- The priorities for the **methodologies** to be taken onboard in WP5 were ranked from 1 (high) to 5 (low) for human health and for environmental studies. The results are shown in the Tables below (Table 7 and Table 8).

Table 7: Ranking of the methodology priorities under WP5 (1=high to 5=low) for human health

Rank for Human Health	1	2	3	4	5
Grouping	11	2	2		
QSAR	3	1			
TK	2	1		1	
Effects of chemicals on the microbiome		1			
Gerontogenic effects on biological age		1			
System Biology		1	1		1

Table 8: Ranking of the methodology priorities under WP5 (1=high to 5=low) for environmental studies

Rank for the Environment	1	2	3	4	5
Grouping	11	1	1		
QSAR	2	1			
TK		1		2	
Effects of chemicals on the microbiome				1	
Gerontogenic effects on biological age					1
System Biology		1			2

- **Identification of needs concerning “Innovation in regulatory risk assessment” (WP6)**
WP6 is made up of 4 tasks.

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 18

Task 6.1 involves Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATAs). The PARC interim GB was asked to rank different toxicological endpoints of higher priority for which IATAs should be developed under this task. The results are presented in the table below (Table 9).

Table 9: Ranking of toxicological endpoints of higher priority for which IATAs should be developed under Task 6.1

Rank	1	2	3
Endocrine disruptors	5	4	3
Neurotox (including developmental neurotox)	3	3	5
Immunotox	2	3	2
Transgenerational effects, epigenetics and delayed effects	4	1	2
Non-genotoxic Carcinogenotoxicity	1	2	1

Task 6.2 is about Integrative exposure and risk assessment (IERA). The PARC interim GB ranked specific case studies of higher priority to be selected to perform integrative exposure and risk assessment. Results are shown in the table below (Table 10).

Table 10: Ranking of case studies of higher priority for IERA under Task 6.2

Ranking	1	2	3	4	Number of citations
PerFluoroAlkylSubstances	4	2	1	1	8
Trace Heavy Metals	4	1			5
Pesticides and biocides	1	5	1		7
Persistent Organic Pollutants of Increasing Concern	1	2	2		5
Fungicides		1	3		4
Flame retardants	1	1		1	3
Phthalates and substitutes			2	1	3
PFAS & Flame retardants				1	1
EDC	1				1
Mycotoxins	1				1
Acrylamide			1		1
CMR and neurotoxic substances			1		1

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 19

Mercury			1		1
Metals in batteries				1	1
Pharmaceutical and personal care products				1	1
Pyrethroids				1	1
Real-life mixtures (generally composed of substances from different chemical families)				1	1

Suggestions for case studies of higher priority to be selected to perform integrative exposure and **ecological** risk assessment were also proposed by the interim GB. Results are presented in the table below (Table 11).

Table 11: Suggestions of case studies for integrative exposure and ecological risk assessment under Task 6.2

Austria	Group of Bisphenols, Group of Alkylphenols
Belgium	PerFluoroAlkylSubstances // Existing as well as newly developed AOPs can be used to characterize the adverse effects of PFAS, in particular their endocrine disrupting properties.
Czech Republic	Flame retardants, PFAS, antiparasitics (Veterinary drugs), azoles, metabolites and mixtures// (In collaboration with WP5) Hier tier effect assessment and risk assessment.
EFSA	Pesticides and fungicides
France	POP
Spain	
Italy	Veterinary pharmaceuticals // Ecosystem effects
Norway	mixture effects and specific CEC determination // Mixture toxicity and combined effects
Portugal	PMT
Slovenia	Integrative exposure and risk assessment of selected emerging contaminants in the groundwater ecosystems // Karst, with its specific bedrock structures, covers approximately 25% of the area of the EU. Aquifers in this area are an important source of drinking water. Karst aquifers are unique and protected ecosystem. The RA of chemicals requires new paradigms due to specific conditions such as lack of light, reduced self-purification and limited ability of stygofauna for re-colonialization
Switzerland	Pesticides/Biocides // Resolve partially conflicting RA methodologies between 1107/2009 and EU WFD

Task 6.3 concerns the Review of risk assessment methodologies. In the table below (Table 12), the different suggestions of case studies under this task are listed.

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 20

Table 12: Suggestions of case studies for the Review of risk assessment methodologies under Task 6.3

Austria	ED CLP criteria and test requirements should be tested for (a) non EATS pathway(s) For many aspects (like ED, long term effects, human and environmental variability ...) the risk cannot be easily quantified in terms of expectable hazard, hazard size and probability to occur. Therefore, consider the review of potential other metrics and risk management options, with an enhanced focus on uncertainty, expectable sustainable socio-economic benefit, climate costs, potential alternative (to) chemicals ..., safe by design. I would see here a link to WP 8.1.
Belgium	In Flanders we have elaborated regulations on the sustainable management of waste, materials and soil. Flanders has a leading position on promoting the circular economy. Existing methodologies for risk assessment could be a test case for evaluating efficiency and coherence of these methods. // Thyroid hormone system disruption // review RA methodologies : bisphenols & analogues across regulations, assess appropriateness scenarios used for biocides & REACH authorisation process incl. dermal exposure risk assessment, effectiveness RMM in real life (e.g. monitoring vs. health workers vs. modelling) // enforcement articles: nanomaterials // health assessment workers in recycling plants e.g. batteries // Comparison of 6 human health risk assessment models (S-RISK, RBCA, RISC 5, MODUL'ERS, CLEA, ENVIRISK) - Feasibility study done for the Walloon Ministry of Environment (SPAQUE, 2020).// EFSA pesticides models' scenarios (for general population scenario – Residents and Bystanders) – Metal shredders risks assessment (including house dust exposure) – Improve the soil-house dust relationship in health risk assessments for pesticides, POPs and heavy metals by acquiring and modelling new environmental data
EFSA	IATA for pyrethroids and fungicides
Finland	A case study under “Tools to help enforcement of legislation with focus on articles”: Review of existing risk assessment tools and databases to identify priority substances and products (articles and materials) for enforcement of legislation (e.g., REACH and POP restrictions). Review of existing analytical testing methods and Identify the needs for development new methods to enforce compliance of different products (in collaboration with 4.2). FIOH proposed also a case study related to the evaluation of the REACH authorization/restriction processes and OSH (CMD/CAD) processes in the management of occupational exposure (strengths and weaknesses of both processes in the management of occupational exposures to prioritized SVHC compounds at workplaces and to identify in which cases REACH authorization, REACH restriction or OSH legislation is the most effective in reducing exposure and risks and what should be done to improve the effectivity of different regulatory measures).
France	At first sight available socio-economic/decision tools for chemicals would work for mixtures, but we could work on a check if the economic / decision support toolbox available so far is adapted for the management of chemicals mixtures or if updates are required (INERIS).
Italy	Pesticides and biocides, as data rich compounds and natural toxins as data poor compounds. in order to have a complete picture in different situations; carcinogenic compounds

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 21

Slovenia	Bisphenol A and its analogs, For ecological risk assessment Integrative exposure and risk assessment of selected emerging contaminants in the groundwater ecosystems.
Spain	Phthalates (linking ECHA assessment under REACH, EFSA assessment for food contact materials, and assessments in medical devices Pyrethroids, combining assessments as pesticides, biocides and veterinary medicines
Switzerland	Relevant effect-biomarker which are currently under characterisation in OECD Occupational Biomonitoring activity (by Robert Pasanen-Kase, SECO and Nancy Hopf, Unisanté, CH)

Task 6.4 is about Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodology. In the table below (Table 13), different suggestions of case studies under this task are listed.

Table 13: PARC interim GB suggestions for case studies under Task 6.4

Austria	Mixtures: monitoring results generated in WP 4 or other projects should be considered as case studies to address mixture toxicity (test MAF applicability); Case studies on mixtures assessments: identifying knowledge gaps to deal with mixtures in the foreseen regulation, how to implement MAF in certain regulation as e.g REACH, maybe use some of the foreseen priority substances as an example for MAF respectively. Case studies on substances with severe knowledge gaps: focus on regulatory needs for some of the priority substances within PARC.
EFSA	Pyrethroids or fungicides
Finland	1) WWTP effluent risk assessment and management through update of treatment techs. 2) Case studies related to mixed exposure at occupational context (in metal sector/recycling). However, it is unclear if this better fits under 6.2
France	At first sight available socio-economic/decision tools for chemicals would work for mixtures, but we could work on a check if the economic / decision support toolbox available so far is adapted for the management of chemicals mixtures or if updates are required (INERIS).
Italy	Mixtures, improve grouping and modelling methodologies
Slovenia	Bisphenol A and its analogs
Switzerland	Use monitoring data to calculate mixture risk and test MAFs; use monitoring data to feedback to registration

4. Feedback from the WPs on their prioritisation strategy for the first years

The objective of this deliverable is to trace how prioritisation of activities, either for substances or methods' selection, was done when defining PARC activities for the first years of PARC.

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 22

4.1 Prioritisation of substances: launch of a dedicated survey

Task 2.1 "Priority Setting" prepared a survey on the criteria used for substance prioritisation. The survey was sent out to the WPLs and TLs (4-5-6) on the 28th of October 2022 (**Annex 4**). The aim was to map out the working strategy and the criteria that helped prioritise the substances/ group of substances within the WPs. The questions were based on four main prioritisation criteria: i) the regulatory status of the substance, ii) its hazardous properties, iii) its exposure characteristics and iv) the technical feasibility. Some questions were common for human health and for the environment, whereas other questions were distinct for each topic. PFAS, metals, pesticides and biocides, endocrine disruptors, bisphenol alternatives and toxins are the six groups of substances already prioritised within PARC as a legacy from HBM4EU. As a consequence, participants had to fill in the survey after having selected one (or more) of these groups of substances. They even had the choice of filling the survey for specific substances within these groups.

4.2 Prioritisation of methods: organisation of bilateral meetings

In order to trace how the prioritisation of methods was done within the Tasks or WPs, discussions took place between October and November 2022 with Task 4.3, WP5, and Tasks 6.1- 6.2- 6.3 and 6.4 co-leaders. These Tasks/WPs include projects related to new methods or tools.

A list of questions was prepared to help gather criteria used for the Prioritisation of Methods. The questions were used during the meeting to facilitate the discussions.

1-How was the prioritisation of methods made within your WP?

2-Did you base your prioritisation strategy on the PARC concept paper⁷ and the results of the survey sent to the PARC interim GB members?

3-How did you contact the partners of your team? Did they come to you after reading the concept paper or did you send a call for interest within your WP?

4-Would you say that the endpoints and areas addressed in your WP are equivalent for human health and environment or some are more specific for human health or the

⁷ Concept paper: After nomination by the Horizon Europe Shadow Programme Committee of country representatives to be involved in the Partnership development, a first meeting was organised by DG R&I in September 2019 to present the idea of the Partnership. At this meeting the development of the Concept Paper for the Partnership was launched and a Steering Group for the Partnership development was created as well as a smaller drafting group. A revised version of the Concept Paper was submitted for approval for publication by the Steering Group in its virtual meeting on 27 May 2020.

Link: [ec_rtd_he-partnerships-chemical-risk-assessment.pdf \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.rtd.he-partnerships-chemical-risk-assessment.pdf)

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 23

environment?

5-Are there any priorities that you could not cover because you did not find partners or resources?

6-How did you avoid the duplication of work?

7-If you had the chance to do the prioritisation again would you do it the same way or do you have things that did not work well?

5. Outcomes of the prioritisation process

5.1 Substances

Seventeen responses to the questionnaire on the prioritisation of substances were sent to ANSES by December 16th 2022. Of the respondents, ten (58.8%) represented WP5 (T5.1- T5.2- T5.3), four (23.5%) stand for WP4 (T4.1) and three (17.7%) for WP6 (T6.1-T6.4).

At the beginning of the survey, participants were asked, for each of the six groups of substances (PFAS, metals, pesticides and biocides, endocrine disruptors, bisphenols alternatives and toxins), to classify the four prioritisation criteria, based on the order of their importance within their prioritisation strategy. The four prioritisation criteria are:

- C1: Regulatory needs
- C2: Hazardous properties
- C3: Exposure characteristics
- C4: Technical feasibility

The ranking of the criteria for the selection of group of substances for human health studies is presented in the table below (Table 14).

Table 14: Ranking of the four criteria for the prioritisation of substances for the human health studies depending on their importance

Group of substances		Level of Importance			
		++++	+++	++	+
PFAS	C1	50%	29%	21%	
	C2	29%	29%	36%	7%
	C3	21%	36 %	43%	
	C4		7%		93%
Metals	C1	50%	14%	29%	7%
	C2	29%	14%	50%	7%

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	C3	21%	50%	21%	7%
	C4			21%	79%
Pesticides and biocides	C1	29%	36%	36%	
	C2	50%	21%	21%	7%
	C3	21%	36%	36%	7%
	C4		7%	7%	86%
Endocrine disruptors	C1	21%	36%	43%	
	C2	57%	21%	14%	7%
	C3	21%	36%	36%	7%
	C4		7%	7%	86%
Bisphenol alternatives	C1	43%	43%	14%	
	C2	43%	29%	21%	7%
	C3	14%	21%	64%	
	C4		7%		93%
Toxins	C1	29%	36%	29%	7%
	C2	43%	21%	29%	7%
	C3	21%	21%	43%	14%
	C4	7%	21%		71%

Legend: ++++ → Highest level of importance

+ → Lowest level of importance

As an example to ease the reading of this table, for PFAS, regulatory needs were, in term of importance, the number one priority criteria for choosing this group according to 50% of the survey respondents, however, they were considered as a second priority criteria for 29% and a third priority criteria for 21%. Also, for 29%, the hazardous properties of the substance were considered as first and second prioritisation criteria whereas it was as a third priority for 36% and a last priority for 7%.

As shown in this table, the importance of the four prioritisation criteria is different depending on the substance/group of substances.

For the environment, the importance of these criteria to prioritise substances was different. Results are presented in the table below (Table 15).

Table 15: Ranking of the four criteria for the prioritisation of group of substances for environmental health studies depending on their importance

Group of substances		Level of Importance			
		++++	+++	++	+
PFAS	C1	43%	14%	36%	7%
	C2	21%	36%	36%	7%

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 25

	C3	36%	36%	29%	
	C4		14%		86%
Metals	C1	36%	14%	43%	7%
	C2	36%	36%	14%	14%
	C3	29%	43%	29%	
	C4		7%	14%	79%
Pesticides and biocides	C1	36%	21%	43%	
	C2	29%	43%	21%	7%
	C3	36%	29%	36%	
	C4		7%		93%
Endocrine disruptors	C1	36%	29%	36%	
	C2	36%	43%	14%	7%
	C3	29%	21%	43%	7%
	C4		7%	7%	86%
Bisphenol alternatives	C1	36%	21%	43%	
	C2	36%	36%	21%	7%
	C3	29%	36%	36%	
	C4		7%		93%

Legend: ++++ → Highest level of importance
+ → Lowest level of importance

In addition to these criteria, participants identified other considerations that helped them prioritise the substances, in particular:

- Data availability and current knowledge gaps
- Crosslinks to activities in other WPs for a mutual selection of prioritised substances
- Partner interests
- Results of HBM4EU for HBM

It has to be noted that, due to the lack of answers, the analysis of the remaining responses to more specific questions had no benefit. For this reason, only the questions whose answers have been shared in this deliverable are mentioned in **Annex 4**.

5.2 Methods

The meeting with **Task 4.3** co-leaders clarified that Suspect Non-Targeted Screening (SNTS) and Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) were explicitly included in the “Strategic Research and

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 26

Innovation Plan for Safe and Sustainable Chemicals and Materials”⁸ document which indicates that these methods are a priority for the European Commission.

Moreover, in addition to the top-down information from the priorities pushing toward these innovative methods, the prioritisation was also a result of bottom-up approaches from the laboratories and the partners involved in the monitoring of food or HBM. Adjustments were made according to the partners’ capacities and resources.

The three main areas (HBM, food and environment) are covered in the projects of this Task but it has to be noted that within these areas there is an interaction with all the WPs. An interaction with Task 4.1 helped identify dry blood spot and silicone wristbands as a priority for innovative sampling methods; this interaction also impacted the choice of the working areas for occupational exposure studies.

The discussions with **WP5** showed that different criteria were used for the prioritisation of methods:

- 1- The endpoints and methods mentioned in the PARC interim GB survey
- 2- The Chemical strategy for sustainability (CSS)⁹
- 3- The existing projects
- 4- The partners and their suggestion

Five endpoints were then defined from which some priorities might be added or removed in following years:

- Endocrine Disruptors, with focus on thyroid because a lot of methods are already developed and partially validated
- Metabolic disruption
- Non-genotoxic carcinogenicity
- Developmental neurotoxicity and neurotoxicity
- Immuno-toxicity

Potential partners were asked if they could contribute significantly to one of the endpoints, then, task leaders compiled the project proposals.

The substances were prioritised according to the results of the survey and the discussions with the three European agencies involved in PARC (EEA, EFSA and ECHA) (EFSA had a high priority on Mycotoxins, ECHA suggested Bisphenols for example), but ongoing projects were also taken into account. PFAS were highly prioritised within WP5, however the Commission has launched a call for proposals under the Green Deal call¹⁰ focused on remediation of

⁸SRIP: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/9f04603f-534b-11ed-92ed-01aa75ed71a1/>

⁹Chemical Strategy for sustainability: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/chemicals-strategy_en

¹⁰European Green Deal: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/delivering-european-green-deal_en

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 27

contamination with persistent and mobile chemicals, including PFAS (deadline date for proposal submission : 27 January 2021). Consequently, PFAS couldn't be included because the results of the many relevant projects and initiatives launched aren't advanced enough yet. This also applies to nanomaterials already addressed in the Malta initiative¹¹ towards safer nanomaterials.

For **Task 6.1**, the priorities came from the PARC interim GB survey. The endpoints for which IATAs will be developed are:

- Endocrine Disruption
- Liver toxicity
- Genotoxicity

The aim is to develop generic IATAs, and adapt different versions for different regulations. Since it is not feasible to deliver IATAs for any sectorial legislation (pesticide, industrial chemicals, cosmetics...), discussions are planned with different regulatory agencies: SCCS, ECHA and EFSA to highlight particular needs for these endpoints.

It has to be noted that the available data is important to make the choice of the endpoint because IATAs consist in the combination of different methods and are driven by what is available and robust. It will also depend on the substances and the crosslinks with other WPs in PARC; for example, WP5 is working on mycotoxins, which can be very genotoxic.

Task 6.1 is planning to have in-depth discussions with WP5 and WP2 concerning additional endpoints for which they have to develop IATAs; and might involve the PARC stakeholder forum in the discussions.

Within **Task 6.2** the prioritisation was done by:

- 1-Making an inventory in a very broad way, of existing models beyond those developed and used by the partners, as well as a more precise inventory of the models developed and used by the partners of the task
- 2-Making links with existing projects on aggregate exposure, source to dose, health impacts...
- 3-Taking into account methods and chemical family priorities from the PARC interim GB survey in addition to other interesting substances to include in some of the projects under this task
- 4-Selecting case studies for which several partners from different countries of Europe are interested

Task 6.3 and **Task 6.4** worked very similarly. They started from the PARC interim GB survey and more precisely from the Excel file that summarise the answers, in combination with the concept paper. They grouped the different answers into clusters and new topics of interest

¹¹ Malta initiative: <https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/international-cooperation/the-malta-initiative/>

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 28

were added. They produced a scoping document and sent it out to potential interested partners, but, not all of the responses ended up as projects and some suggestions were merged. At the end, discussions with WPLs as well as with the three EU agencies involved in PARC helped define the final projects suggested for inclusion in the PARC rolling SRIA.

6. Discussion

To sum-up, the substances/ group of substances and the methods prioritised within the different work packages of PARC were based on different criteria. The majority of these criteria were common for all the WPs, a few were specific to some suggested projects to be implemented under PARC.

Below is a list of the criteria regardless of their order of importance:

- Results from the 3rd round of prioritisation done under the HBM4EU project,
- The methods, endpoints and substances prioritised in the results from the PARC interim GB survey,
- The Commission's "Chemical Strategy for Sustainability" and the "Strategic Research and Innovation Plan for Safe and Sustainable Chemicals and Materials" documents,
- The regulatory needs identified by WPL/TL according to their WP/Task objectives,
- The hazardous properties and characteristics of the substances,
- The available data and the knowledge gaps,
- The partners' interests, their capacities and resources,
- The interaction and crosslinks with other WPs or Tasks within PARC,
- The scientific activities done outside PARC: Checking the progress of ongoing projects in areas relevant to PARC can help identify gaps, avoid duplication and promote synergies. PARC WPLs and TLs are aware of possible duplication; to avoid this, they make sure they include in the suggested projects to be implemented in PARC leaders or partners from other initiatives,
- The results of discussions with regulatory agencies (e.g.: SCCS, ECHA, EEA, EFSA, etc.).

At the date of the submission of this deliverable, topics covered under each WP are represented in the table below (Table 16). A more detailed presentation, specifying the Projects covering these Substances/ Group of substances under the WPs is proposed in **Annex 5**. It is important to note that this is the very beginning and the partnership aims to address as many issues as possible.

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 29

Table 16: Substances / Group of substances covered under each WP

Substances / Group of substances	WP4	WP5	WP6
Biocides	✓	✓	✓
Pharmaceuticals / Hazardous medicinal products	✓		✓
Veterinary pharmaceuticals			✓
Plant protection products	✓	✓	✓
PFAS	✓		✓
BPA, BPA analogues, BPA alternatives, Bisphenols	✓	✓	✓
Natural Toxins		✓	✓
Metals	✓		✓
Mercury	✓		
Arsenic	✓		
Phthalates	✓		✓
Flame retardants			✓
Endocrine Disrupting Compounds (EDC)	✓	✓	✓
Metabolic Disrupting Compounds (MDC)		✓	
Emerging chemicals	✓		
Mixtures	✓	✓	✓
Food contact material		✓	✓
Cosmetics		✓	✓
PBT/vPvB	✓		✓

As seen, many WPs deal with the same substances and / or groups of substances, for this reason, it is necessary to build communication links to ensure synergies, avoid duplication and especially join and optimise effort.

One of the strengths of PARC is that it includes in its scope activities not only dealing with monitoring and exposure to chemicals but also with hazard and risk assessment, for human health and for the environment. However, it doesn't mean that all the substances that are included in the PARC rolling SRIA have to be addressed in all WPs, and especially WPs 4, 5, 6 or 8. Activities done under PARC should answer specific knowledge needs or data gaps and, therefore, it may happen that for some compounds or families, the dataset on hazard is limited whereas for other compounds, missing data are more related to exposure. On the contrary for some compounds, in particular emerging ones, transversal activities across WPs

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 30

4-5-6 and 8 will be necessary, this will constitute a good example on how PARC can integrate all the aspects of risk assessment.

One limitation concerning the selection of the compounds for the first annual work plan of PARC is that it was mainly driven by the human biomonitoring community as part of the HBM4EU legacy. Efforts were also done to get priorities from the environmental community, for example, through the PARC interim GB. However, it should be recognised that, at the start of the partnership, there was still a slight imbalance between representativeness of the human health community compared to the environmental health community, this will be adjusted as needed as we move forward.

Concerning methods, as for substances, the initial prioritisation was carried out before the beginning of PARC. As explained above and in order to prepare this deliverable, a survey was prepared, which included questions related to different criteria that WP co-leaders might have used to prioritise their compounds, whereas, for methods, conducting a survey was not convenient. For this reason, discussions with the WP co-leaders were carried out to get explanations and to trace what was done in order to define common criteria.

Identifying priorities (either for methods or compounds) does not mean that PARC will be able to address them; adequate resources (expert knowledge and co-funding capacities) should indeed be sufficient to take over these priorities. The priorities have to be endorsed by WPLs and the Coordination Team in order to identify partners that can address them, hoping that they will also have the necessary resources to co-finance the activity/projects built to address a priority. Therefore, the bottom up approach may be an issue if some institutions define new projects or are interested in taking part in projects to be implemented in PARC but they don't always have the co-funding available.

Another limitation of the prioritisation performed before the launch of PARC, or at the very beginning, was the limited time to carry out that process, as the delay for the submission of the PARC proposal were very constrained and did not leave enough time to implement an in-depth process. WP and Task leaders need time to identify what is really needed, what is available in terms of methods and what is already addressed in other projects outside PARC to avoid duplication.

It is also important to mention that some priorities were left out to avoid duplication with other on-going activities outside PARC and optimise use of results. For example, in WP5, PFAS were prioritised quite highly, but as the Green Deal projects¹⁰ already address this group, WP5

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 31

co-leaders decided not to work on PFAS for the time being because those projects are not in the finalisation phase and their results are not available yet. However, maybe PFAS will become a priority later in PARC. It is the same for nanomaterials because the Malta initiative is for example already doing a lot. Within T5.3, concerning the modeling of AOPs and IATAs, there is a constant exchange with OECD, EFSA and with the regulators to see if new information are coming up. At the moment IATA for DNT is under development; for ED and thyroid there is a good AOP network already existing; for metabolic disruption the OECD is working on it over the next 5 years; for non-genotoxic carcinogenicity IATA has been published¹² and some PARC partners are coauthors; for respiratory sensitisation and developmental and reproductive toxicity there are ongoing initiatives as well. In conclusion, AOPs and IATAs might change depending on the endpoints prioritised.

Finally, another issue is the disparity between the 'priority compounds' and the 'priority endpoints' not perfectly aligned in PARC. Bisphenols are prioritised compounds. However, this group was not included as part of ED endpoint studies and was not prioritised although it has an important impact on reproductive toxicology. This could have been better addressed if communicated from the beginning.

It is worth highlighting that, despite the prioritisation of substances and methods that took place prior to the launch of this partnership, all projects have been discussed, particularly within Task 2.1, which has established a formal process for the review of new projects under PARC. This process is a living document that could be improved on a regular basis.

7. Conclusion and Perspective

Prioritisation is key as PARC has been elaborated to specifically address regulatory/policy needs at EU and/or National level. Based on the legacy of HBM4EU, PARC will continue to work on prioritised compounds and families for which data gaps are identified or to follow the impact of some management measures to reduce exposure. Besides these compounds, PARC will also generate datasets and develop tools to identify emerging chemicals that could be a risk either for human health and/or for the environment. PARC will also provide support to the Commission on the Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) strategy and its implementation based on the recent criteria published by the Commission. This new approach

¹² Publication on IATA for non-genotoxic carcinogenic chemical substances: [International regulatory needs for development of an IATA for non-genotoxic carcinogenic chemical substances - PubMed \(nih.gov\)](#)

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 32

will promote the reuse of chemicals or materials, which may generate new exposure scenarios or new compounds (e.g. transformation or degradations products).

PARC also aims to develop new methods to assess the hazard or the exposure to chemicals by reducing / avoiding animal testing. PARC will not be able to deal with all the needs for all methods and some endpoints have already been selected. NAMs will target these specific endpoints while taking into account the future prioritisation rounds and the ongoing projects or initiatives outside PARC. In addition, new priorities might be identified for the following years of PARC.

For the upcoming years, the prioritisation process will follow several steps (Figure 2):

Mapping of needs: Targeted surveys, focused workshops or discussion groups will be organised to gather information needs for policy-makers and risk assessors at both EU and national level, as well as stakeholders and experts involved in chemical risk assessment (RA) activities.

Task 2.1 partners will ensure that the policy and regulatory links are there, in close collaboration with the PARC Coordination Team (CT), the National Hubs (NHs) and, Task 2.2 to warrant the adequate identification of regulatory demands under a science to policy dialogue. During the 7 years of the partnership, 2-3 rounds of mapping of needs and prioritisation are planned.

Scoring/ranking activities based on specific priority criteria: Based on the mapping of needs, Task 2.1 will score/rank substances/groups and methods/innovative tools for which data gaps and/or knowledge needs have been identified. The criteria for prioritisation will be based on policy and regulatory relevance, feasibility, and the fact that the projects implemented under PARC deliver outputs in coherence with the overall goals of PARC. Other priority criteria might be added.

Preparing background documents: For prioritised substances background documents will be prepared together with the Chemical Leaders (CLs)¹³, to specify what are the data gaps and knowledge needs related to the substances or groups and, to summarise the main elements concerning their regulatory status, chemical and hazard properties, principal exposure scenarios and potential risks. These background documents will then evolve to “Scoping Documents”, which should describe more specific policy/regulatory questions and then map the ongoing or foreseen activities planned at EU and/or national levels to which PARC can

¹³ Chemical Leaders are experts in charge of following the work on a specific chemical substance/group of chemical substances, reporting on the results and challenges encountered and closely monitoring and identifying communication and dissemination of the results.

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 33

contribute and the gaps that can be filled by PARC. The Scoping Document will also envisage which synergies should be developed.

For methods/tools, policy and regulatory needs will be documented with the support of the Methodology Leaders (MLs)¹⁴ based on the surveys as a basis for the scoring/ranking.

One of the main challenges of PARC is to show that for the prioritised substances PARC could address data gaps that are related to any step in the risk assessment process: hazard, exposure (for humans or the environment) and risk assessment. Some substances are already well known, therefore, for these substances, not all steps have to be completed (e.g.: for pesticides and biocides, as the toxicity data required under the specific legislations is already quite rich, WP5 did not focus these groups but have targeted other substances/groups less investigated up to now).

Another important challenge for PARC is to be flexible and react quickly if additional needs are identified. It is the purpose of the Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM) included in PARC to allow any national and European policy-makers to submit a request for specific information to the PARC Consortium outside of the formal timeframes.

Figure 2: Prioritisation process for the upcoming years of PARC

¹⁴ Methodology Leaders are experts in charge of following the work on a specific new approach methodology(ies), reporting on the results and challenges encountered and closely monitoring and identifying communication and dissemination possibilities of the results.

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 34

Annexes

Annex 1: Project Life Cycle

Figure 3: Process for project reviewing and the life cycle of the project

The project initiation begins with the WPLs/TLs, which are responsible for identifying projects to answer to priorities. The Initiation phase Template of the project is then submitted to Task 2.1 for review. The MB decides to either accept the project as it is, reject it or ask for a revision before it can be accepted, *via* a dedicated Decision Memo. If the project is accepted to move forward, it will enter the planning/implementation phase and will then be included in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). The progress of the implementation of all projects will be monitored by the reviewers/MB and reported in the Annual Work Plan (AWP) and the Annual Summary Report (ASR).

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 35

Annex 2: Short list of 25 substances within the 3rd prioritisation round of HBM4EU

Substance name	Single substance	Group	No of nominations	Actors that nominated substance		
				EU Policy Board	National Hubs	Stakeholders
1 Mercury	x		4		Iceland, Spain,	
2 Trace/heavy metals (e.g.: Al, Co, Mn, Cd, Pb, Cu, Zn, Ni, Cr, W, natural U, Bi, Beryllium, manganese, nickel, arsenic, lithium, vanadium, antimony); Metals in batteries: cobalt (Co), Nickel, (Ni), Lithium (Li).		x	14	DG Grow (Cr VI), DG Sante (lead, cadmium, cobalt, barium, aluminium)	Lithuania (Mn, Cr VI only), Iceland (Cd only), Estonia (Cr VI, Pb), Hungary (Pb), Sweden (Pb), Latvia	ETUI (Cr VI)
3 Nanoforms of Co and Ni		x	3	DG Employment	Sweden, Finland	
4 Aluminium and manganese: occupational		x	4	DG Employment	Finland, Luxembourg,	
5 Acrylamide	x		4		Iceland, Israel,	
6 PFAS		x	23	DG Environment, DG SANTE, EEA	Israel, Belgium, Cyprus, Netherlands, Finland, Denmark, Spain, UK, Norway, Hungary, Portugal,	HEAL, ETUI, Chem Trust
7 Flame retardants: Brominated flame retardants, Organophosphate flame retardants, Flame retardants (including TDCPP, TBBPA) (DBDPE, Decabromo-diphenyl ethane, CAS: 84852-53-9, EC: 284-366-9)		x	11	EEA	Germany, Belgium, Finland, Denmark, Spain, Hungary, Austria, Italy	HEAL, Chem Trust
8 Pesticides and biocides, with focus on glyphostae, pyrethroides, carbamate, Dithiocarbamates, organophosphates and lindane		x	11	ECHA, EEA, EFSA	Belgium, Denmark, UK, Israel, Portugal, Italy	HEAL, ETUI
9 Fungicides: includes SDHI fungicides (boscalid, bixafen, fluxapyroxad); Azoles (imazalil, ipconazole, metconazole, penconazole, prochloraz, tebuconazole, tetraconazole); Dithiocarbamates; Famoxadone and Dimoxystrobin; Isothiazolinones (CIT/MIT, BIT), Triazole derivative metabolites (TDM)		x	4	DG Environment, E	France, Germany, Slovenia	
10 Phthalates and substitutes, FCM phthalate substitutes, DEHTP (Bis(2-ethylhexyl) terephthalate) CAS 6422-86-2		x	6	DG Environment, DG SANTE, EEA	Cyprus, Germany	
11 Industrial solvents (e.g. BTEX metabolites, dry cleaning solvents, paint solvents)		x	3	DG Employment	Luxembourg, Estonia	
12 Persistent Organic Pollutants of Increasing Concern such as Dechloranes, Chlorinated paraffins and Chloronaphtalene, Dioxins and PCB		x	4		France, Norway, Sweden, Estonia	
13 Synthetic fragrances (OTNE-Tetramethyl acetyloctahydronaphthalene, Galaxolide, Lysmeral/Lilial CAS 80-54-6, Polycyclic musks, Lyril CAS 31906-04-4, Hydroxycitronellal CAS 107-75-5, Isoeugenol CAS 97-54-1)		x	5	DG Employment	France, Germany, Norway	WECF
14 UV filters (salicylates, cinnamates and benzophenones).		x	3		France, Israel, Iceland	
15 Mixtures (including contaminants e.g. Mycotoxins and plant contaminants, and air pollutants with EDC properties)		x	6	JRC	Netherlands, Hungary, Austria	
16 Medical substances: occupational		x	1	DG Employment		
17 Pyrazoles		x	1	ECHA		
18 PAH		x	4		Cyprus, UK,	ETUI
19 Bisphenols (BADGE/DGEBA, Bisphenol-A-diglycidylether / Diglycidylether of Bisphenol A, CAS Number: 1675-54-3 EC Number: 216-823-5 and Tetrabromo-bisphenol A (TBBPA); 3-1 Tetrabromobisphenol A)		x	5	ECHA	Belgium, Spain, Portugal	Chem Trust
20 Emerging substances, unknowns, non-targeted screening		x	7	Environment, EEA, JRC	Belgium, Denmark, Austria	
21 Substances with potential to bioaccumulate in air-breathing organisms		x	1	ECHA		
22 Nanomaterials, nanoplastics, nano titanium dioxide		x	2	DG Env	Spain	
23 Mycotoxins, in particular Ochratoxin A (CAS 303-47-9).		x	3	EFSA	Portugal, Austria	
24 Emerging and endocrine active mycotoxins.		x	1	DG Grow		
25 Endocrine disruptors		x	1	DG Grow		
25 Styrene	x		2	DG SANTE	Slovenia	
26 MOAH Mineral oil aromatic hydrocarbons		x	1	DG SANTE		

Table 17: Short list of 25 substances from the 3rd prioritisation round of HBM4EU

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 36

Annex 3: Interim GB's suggestions for activities to be developed under task 4.3

Table 18: The interim GB's suggestions for activities to be developed under Task 4.3 for the first three years of PARC

FR	<p>Improve current performances and harmonization of suspect and non-targeted screening method. Particularly, 1) use of in vitro cell-based assays for detection of EDCs and dioxin-like compounds in environmental matrices (waste and surface waters, sediments, soils) and their application in environmental monitoring programs, including in WFD context, at both national and European scales. 2) Combination of in vitro assays with physico-chemical methods within bioanalytical strategies (e.g. effect-directed analysis or EDA) to direct chemical identification of effective compounds in prioritized samples (e.g. hotspots). Contribution to the development of a generic framework for both environmental and HBM, from effect-based assessment to EDA. Experience in applying suspect screening approaches in environmental campaign and interested to extend to early warning system for this field. Applying non-target screening approaches in environmental field (including soils). Evaluate in vitro toxicological potential of real PM samples (collected at the emission source, in ambient air or from real source aging experiments) using cellular and acellular models with several targeted endpoints. Evaluate the impact of selected PM sources on a multi-organ model system (Zebrafish) and link the biological (in vitro/in vivo) and acellular responses together, as well as with the PM chemical composition of the different aerosol sources (cf. 5.2). A previously mentioned, analytics on nanomaterials in organic matrix should also be proposed as a priority.</p>
DE	<p>We recommend activities related to effect-based approaches and non-target screening to support regulatory environmental monitoring programs for detecting pollutants and mixtures of pollutants (e.g. under the WFD) and novel approaches in trend monitoring, including early warning systems. Results of ongoing and future national research activities in these areas should be exchanged actively in the PARC network. In the field of HBM new methods for prioritised chemicals of current concern need to be developed if no sensitive and specific method is available.</p>
BE	<p>Explore the use of silicone wristbands (and other tools) for personal exposure assessments, at least in some studies. There is a lot of new literature from very good teams https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30639062/ https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33254690/ // Methods and tools should be user-friendly and easy to apply in practice. // Promote the use of non-targeted analysis in available human and environmental samples; Develop and implement new methodologies for data processing for non-targeted analysis; Foster the collaboration between environmental monitoring and biomonitoring programs in the development and implementation of non-targeted screening methods and annotation libraries; Combining biological activity screening tools with data from non-targeted screening with high resolution mass spectrometry to identify relevant emerging substances/unknowns // Design analytical methods for monitoring co-occurrence of substances, their metabolites and degradation products (e.g. biocides) and implement these when possible in collaboration with existing monitoring programs. // harmonised food consumption surveys, methodology for combined and aggregate exposure assessment, innovate exposure assessment methods, e.g. using big data // Promote links between HBM data and environmental data, health survey for the general population as well as specific subgroups showing potentially intense exposure // A large screening of emerging chemicals in food would allow to evaluate the dietary exposure. Next, these data can be combined with occurrence data of other exposure pathways to allow a profound risk assessment. These data will support both EFSA and EU Policy. // Effect Based Monitoring (EBM)</p>

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WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 37

	with biotests is useful in case of complex wastewaters. Biotests are applied to entire environmental samples and they take into account the combined effects of different substances (also metabolites and by-products) that may be present in environmental samples (mixture toxicity). Also the effect of substances that cannot be analysed, identified or quantified is taken into account. The advantages of the concept of EBM have led to the development of biotests throughout the world. In several countries, acute toxicity tests are already applied in national legislation or permitting. Within the European IED legislation, the EBM concept has been included in monitoring effluent strategies within several BREFs, o.a. the BREF for the chemical industry and the textiles BREF. Unfortunately, in BREFs of other complex sectors (like waste treatment), it was concluded that too little monitoring data were available and that the test methodology/ toxicity evaluation is not standardised. Under PARC, there could be an attempt to standardise the test methodology and to agree on trigger values/ emission limit values in wastewater and surface water ((at least for acute toxicity). Maybe it could also be possible to organise workshops or trainings for ecotoxicity labs and authorities. Work could be done on other endpoints than acute toxicity (endpoint like endocrine disruption mutagenicity, genotoxicity). // Suspect and non-target screening: Non-target screening (NTS) including suspect screening has already shown its feasibility in detection and identifying emerging contaminants. Nevertheless, there are some limitations. At present, there is no common procedure on how to prioritise substances identified within non-target screening efforts. There is a need for harmonised non-target screening protocols. An extra support from PARC to the labs that take initiatives in the field of non-target and suspect screening would be welcome.
SW	Focus on emerging pollutants that have not yet been subject to regulation.
CZ	Development of harmonised approaches is crucial – sample preparation and analytical methods do not have to be identical but complementary, data analysis (including building open-access libraries and data processing pipelines) has to be harmonised to enhance the impact of newly generated data.
DG sante	Human biomonitoring of mixtures whether mycotoxins or pesticides as per DG SANTE's requests above may necessitate the development of innovative methods and tools to accurately measure exposure
IT	Use of hair for monitoring long-term cumulative exposure to pesticides/fungicides/other pollutants ; The parallel application of non-target screening methods with effect based tools methods for human and environmental monitoring with the aim to integrate human and ecotoxicological risk assessment and derive trigger values based on toxic units.
AU	see original text, several pages ...
SL	Include deciduous teeth as a matrix for determination of exposure biomarkers. The skeletal compartment is an important chemical repository, making calcified tissues important for measuring exposure. Teeth have been used to estimate long-term cumulative exposure to metals and some organic chemicals. Recent methodologies offer insight into specific life stages and have the potential to reconstruct previous exposure during early life stages (a retrospective temporal exposome). Include validated biomarkers of effect and markers of susceptibility (genetic polymorphisms). Link all three types of biomarkers within the examined populations, in particular in vulnerable populations and populations at naturally or anthropogenically contaminated hot spots. Consider including nutritional markers as markers of nutritional status and exposure to chemicals contained in different foods. Compounds specific stable isotopes and stable isotopes of "heavier" elements (Pb, Hg, etc) for tracing their environmental pathways and human exposure. This should be further elaborated with the establishment of a database and other data contained in WP7. To apply the small-area geographical analysis of population-based cancer incidence data in connection with environmental factors as an exemplification replicable to other exposure - health outcomes; to examine and further to identify the methodologies most suitable

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 38

	for risk assessment taking into the account different datasets available. Within the activities already suggested for the Task 4.2 our proposed example could be possibly included in activities 4, 5 and 6. But a separate activity can be formed as well. Assessment of risk of micro (nano)plastics based on ability to penetrate through biological membranes. Development of passive sampling devices for assessment of external exposure to prioritized chemicals / intended for targeted, nontargeted and suspect screening
SWZ	Relate the biomonitoring values to the found toxic effects in vitro and in vivo data; Combination of Effect Based Methods with chemical group-based methods, online chemical and biomonitoring; Appropriate suspect lists based on production, consumption, exposure data as far as available through REACH, industry, etc., automatic non-target screening workflows including prioritization tools that include toxicity information and quality checks to reduce false positives and false negatives
SP	Methods for mixtures and emerging chemicals, Analytical methods to determine simultaneously chemicals from different groups/families. Regarding exposure, improvements should be made regarding measuring and modelling data for specific situations. This include adequate selection of exposure models for exposure estimation and suitable sampling and analytical methodologies when monitoring exposure. Additionally, the development of new methods and tools to account different sources and routes of exposure, not only from individual substances but also from multiple substances, may help to address the uncertainties regarding the risks of combined exposure.
EFSA	See above for specific environmental protections goals that would guide the testing and marketing of new products (incl. the assessment of environmental risk by applicants). Population to be monitored: bystanders and residents, operators, workers; exposure as a standard model approach to be considered
PT	Use of integrative exposure modelling tools e.g. TREXMO (CH) to identify deviations among different models outputs, applicable to OSH and consumers; how to monitor exposure to chemical mixtures in OSH settings e.g. e-waste recycling
FIN	Method for the determination of total PFAS derived from precursors, water samples primary interest (THL) Passive sampling methods, especially as an alternative/ complementary to biota and/or sediment monitoring. Effect-based methods suitable for detecting and setting risk levels of specific substances/groups of substances either as water quality criteria or emission level values (WWTPs).
POL	The search for new biomarkers of chemical exposure in both general populations and in workers exposed to chemicals in the workplace. Metabolomics, lipidomics, molecular biology studies
NO	Recommendations and certifications for EDA (effect directed analysis) based exposure and risk assessment monitoring, Identification criteria for priority CECs, Adjusted monitoring and screening protocol (occupational as well as general populations)
DK	Innovative sampling methods and approaches for individual to community exposure; Improving performances of conventional quantitative targeted methods; In vitro bioassays for effect-based monitoring; suspect screening approaches; Non-target screening approaches

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 39

Annex 4: Survey on the criteria for the prioritisation of substances within the first years of PARC

Only the questions whose answers have been shared in this deliverable are shown in the Annex.

Respondent profile

2. Name *

3. WP number *

4. Task number *

5. Organisation name *

6. If you are back on the survey and clicked on "send another response" please click on "fill the questionnaire for a new substance" *

- Respond to the general questions on prioritization
- Fill the questionnaire for a new substance

General prioritization criteria: Human health (informative)

Please organise the following criteria by weight value (1 being the most important)

7. PFAS *

8. Metals *

9. Pesticides and biocides *

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WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 40

10. Endocrine disruptors *

Hazardous properties
Technical feasibility
Exposure characteristics
Regulatory needs

11. Bisphenols alternatives *

Hazardous properties
Exposure characteristics
Regulatory needs
Technical feasibility

12. Toxines *

Technical feasibility
Regulatory needs
Exposure characteristics
Hazardous properties

16. Endocrine disruptors *

Regulatory needs
Exposure characteristics
Hazardous properties
Technical feasibility

17. Bisphenols alternatives *

Regulatory needs
Technical feasibility
Exposure characteristics
Hazardous properties

General prioritization criteria: environment (informative)

Please organise the following criteria by weight value (1 being the most important)

13. PFAS *

Regulatory needs
Hazardous properties
Technical feasibility
Exposure characteristics

14. Metals *

Regulatory needs
Technical feasibility
Exposure characteristics
Hazardous properties

15. Pesticides and biocides *

Regulatory needs
Hazardous properties
Exposure characteristics
Technical feasibility

D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 41

Annex 5: List of the projects covering Substances/ Group of substances under the different WPs

Table 19: List of the Projects covering Substances/ Group of substances under the different WPs

Substances / Group of substances	WP4	WP5	WP6
Biocides (including disinfection products and cleaning products)	P4.1.1.4.c	P5.2.1.d	P6.2.2.a
			P6.3.1.a - P6.3.1.b - P6.3.2.a
			P6.4.1.a
Pharmaceuticals / Hazardous medicinal products (including cytotoxic drugs and inhalation anesthetics)	P4.1.1.4.c		P6.4.1.a
Veterinary pharmaceuticals			P6.3.2.a
Plant protection products	P4.1.1.2.a	P5.2.1.d	P6.2.1.a - P6.2.2.a - P6.2.3.a - P6.2.4.a
			P6.3.1.b - P6.3.2.a
			P6.4.1.a - P6.4.4.a - P6.4.4.b - P6.4.4.c - P6.4.4.d - P6.4.4.e
PFAS	P4.1.1.2.a		P6.2.1.a - P6.2.2.a - P6.2.3.a - P6.2.4.a
	P4.2.a		P6.3.1.a
Bisphenol A, BPA, BPA analogues, BPA alternatives, Bisphenols	P4.1.1.2.a - P4.1.1.4.a	P5.1.1.b - P5.1.2.b	P6.2.2.a - P6.2.4.a
		P5.2.1.b	P6.3.1.a
Natural toxins (<i>Alternaria</i> toxins, Enniatins)		P5.1.1.a - P5.1.2.a - P5.1.2.B	P6.2.2.a - P6.2.3.a - P6.2.4.a

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D2.1: Prioritisation criteria report	Dissemination level: Public
WP2: A common science-policy-agenda	Version: 2
Main Authors: Christophe ROUSSELLE, Maria TANNOUS	Page: 42

Metals	P4.1.1.2.a - P4.1.1.4.a		P6.2.1.a - P6.2.2.a - P6.2.3.a - P6.2.4.a
Mercury	P4.1.1.2.a - P4.1.3.1.a		
Arsenic	P4.1.1.2.a		
Phthalates	P4.1.1.2.a		P6.2.4.a P6.3.1.a
Flame retardants			P6.2.1.a - P6.2.4.a
Endocrine Disrupting Compounds	P4.2.a	P5.1.1.b	P6.1.1.b
		P5.2.1.b - P5.2.1.c	P6.2.3.a - P6.2.4.a
		P5.3.4.a	P6.3.1.b
Metabolic Disrupting Compounds		P5.2.1.b	
		P5.3.4.a	
Emerging chemicals	P4.1.1.2.a - P4.1.5.a		
	P4.3.2.a		
Mixtures (including chemical mixtures and real-life mixtures)	P4.1.1.2.a	P5.1.2.b	P6.2.3.a - P6.2.4.a
	P4.3.1.a - P4.3.2.a - P4.3.3.a		P6.3.1.b
			P6.4.1.a - P6.4.1.b
Food contact material		P5.2.1.d	P6.2.2.a
			P6.3.1.a
			P6.4.1.a
Cosmetics		P5.2.1.d	P6.3.1.b
			P6.4.1.a
PBT/vPvB	P4.2.a		P6.3.2.a

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